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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, XIV

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This note is a progress report for the DS-reductions after more thorough tests with the provisional data.

1. Introduction

As described in an A&A paper, the 'provisional' data used for testing the main reductions have also been used to begin some double star processing. The completion of the full chain (up to the first sphere solution) of the main reductions enabled a first derivation of Case History Files (CHF) for a number of known and suspected doubles. These CHF:s were then used as input to the two main DS-reduction programs: STDDBL for the known doubles and SEEKDBL for suspected non-singles. In this way, some 1000 known close ($\text{sep} < 10$ arcsec, single IFOV-pointing) doubles had their parameters (primary position and parallax, relative position of secondary, plus magnitudes) determined. Using SEEKDBL, a list of 340 'new' doubles (not listed as such in the IC) likewise had their preliminary parameters determined, and a larger number of suspects were declared (so far) as single. These SEEKDBL single-star positions and parallaxes could also be compared with the sphere-solution data, and the differences were found to be mostly below 10 mas. Because the CHF:s do not directly use the abscissae from the great-circle reductions, such a close agreement is a strong case for the general validity of the complex CHF-generation process.

In these first solutions (May/June -91), the programs were used as developed by previous simulations. Since then, I have tried to optimize their parameters and solution-logic to the 'real' CHF:s, as described below. Also, some further changes in the CHF-generation process have been implemented or are foreseen, and I have made the first multiple-star solutions. A general problem is that most of the programs are closely interrelated, meaning that changes in one unit may have consequences in several other. It is no simple task to make sure that all interfaces make sense, and the progress has been slower than I would have wished. Judging from the present solution-results as compared with those reported in A&A there *is* certainly a progress, however. The details are summarized as follows.

2. Flagging of non-singles

For lack of time, a non-optimal OTF-calibration was used for the provisional CHF-generation. The effect on the CHF:s is believed to be minor, but the flagging of the suspected non-singles was more directly affected. The 'histograms' produced from the $\Delta\chi^2$ -differences between 5- and 3-parameter model fits were not flat, and the 'histogram-parameters' T_h and T_t had another distribution than expected. By combining them with the T_m -criterion (the difference between the 'constant-term' and the 'first-harmonic' magnitudes), however, a reasonably sensitive total selection-criterion was defined and used for the CHF-generation.

Later, the OTF-calibration (made at RGO) has been improved, and the new histogram-parameters have distributions much more as expected. This is shown in Figs 1 and 2, which give the T_h -distribution versus Δm_{eff} from a simulation and from the present version of the provisional data. An important feature of Fig 2 is that the Δm_{eff} 's are calculated from *solution* separations and magnitude-differences, thus removing most of the Δm -uncertainties in the IC-data. To see the 'single-star' distribution more clearly, the IC-data has been retained at Δm_{eff} 's > 5 where there are no actual solutions.

Fig. 1. T_h versus Δm_{eff} for known doubles in the provisional data

Fig. 2. T_h versus Δm_{eff} from a simulation of 9 months of Hipparcos data

Using these new data, I have made extensive double-star selection experiments. In the end, a simple discrimination through planes in the T_h, T_t, T_m -space seems close

to optimal. In practice thus, an object is flagged for possible duplicity whenever a combined criterion $T_c \equiv T_m + a_1 T_h + a_2 T_t$ exceeds a certain limit. In this way, a slightly better double-star discrimination is obtained (as measured by the fraction of known doubles among the flagged objects), but the T_m -criterion still seems to be the most important input. A new determination of the a_i -coefficients (and corrections of T_h and T_t for magnitude- and n_f -effects) will be made when the whole 1-year data set is available.

3. The CHF-generation

The CHF-generation uses some 10 different programs in a complex chain (cf. NDAC/LO/132). This chain was successfully run through in May, giving the set of CHF:s that serve as input for all the solution experiments reported below. Before the 1-year data are put through, there are several points that need improvement. Among the finished ones, the above changes in the flagging-criteria have been implemented in SELSYS1. Also, a systematic comparison between IC-, starmapper-, and solution-data has to be made when the 'ICSPEC' catalogue is updated in MKCAT2. This involves a new 'ICUPD'-program reading solution results from STDDBL and SEEKDBL. In this connection, some of the 'administrative' fields in ICSPEC have been redefined. Among pending points may be listed:

1. An improved version of the Input Catalogue should be used as a basis for the ICSPEC-file. (IC 8 lacks double star flags for several bright stars).
2. Multiple star data from the IC and starmapper have to be stored in a special 'MULSTAR'-file, which needs one or more new programs, cf. section 6.
3. The parametrization of the photometric calibration is not yet finalized, which makes for changes in MKCAL23 and CHF DAT.

Because of the central role played by the CHF:s, all modifications have to be done carefully, with frequent tests to ensure the correct working of the programs.

4. The STDDBL program

The STDDBL program contains a lot of selection-parameters for accepting or rejecting 'possible' solutions. (The LS-processing is started with many different a priori positions for the components, and a non-trivial logic describes the iterations). The original A&A solutions were made without much experimenting, but I have since made many more tests with different logic and parameters. In this way, the computing-times have been reduced by about a factor five, while even increasing the 'yield' of good solutions. Somewhat unexpectedly, a very 'liberal' acceptance criterion for the fit to the observations (parameters $C_1 - C_4$ in NDAC/LO/124) gives the best results, but this may be due partly to the method used for counting the 'good' solutions. Only IC- (and sometimes starmapper-) data are available as a comparison, but the solutions are naturally biased towards these same start values.

As a compromise, one may take the (not so extreme) C -values giving the minimum computing time per 'good' solution. For close (single IFOV-pointing) doubles, this means getting about 1070 double-star solutions (plus 450 primary star positions) in 3.7 hours of CPU-time, using the 1903 CHF:s with at least 10 FOV-crossings. (In June, I got about 900 comparable solutions). The mesh-search radii are set to twice the the estimated mean errors in the a priori data, and sizeable

increases are *not* worthwhile. (The computing times get very long, and only a few tens of new solutions are obtained). The systems that do not get solutions mostly have too few or too ill-distributed scans to give any chance of success, and there is no reason to make a big effort before more complete observations are available.

In A&A, no results for wider (2 IFOV-pointings) doubles were reported. Presently, I obtain about 170 solutions from 260 CHF:s with at least 20 FOV-crossings (10 per pointing for consistency with the single-pointing results). An important test of the STDDBL-program is again obtained from comparisons with the provisional sphere-solution. A component of a wide double may be considered as 'disturbed' by the alternately observed component, at an 'effective' magnitude difference (not to be confused with Δm_{eff}) $\Delta m_e = \Delta m + \Delta m(\text{IFOV})$, where $\Delta m(\text{IFOV})$ is the IFOV attenuation at the component separation. Fig 3 is a plot of the position-differences (DS-Sphere sol.) versus Δm_e for about 50 primary and 10 secondary components with sphere solution data. As expected, the positions agree for large Δm_e , while for larger disturbances, the sphere-solution results are probably erroneous. (This figure gives a concrete demonstration of the effects of 'veiling glare' in the Hipparcos data).

Fig. 3. Position differences (in $\alpha \cos \delta$ and δ) between the DS reductions and the sphere solution for wide double components.

5. The SEEKDBL program

For SEEKDBL, an obvious test is to use it on known doubles. A sample of 889 doubles with 'good' STDDBL-solutions has been used to give some estimates of its efficiency. After roughly optimizing some acceptance-limits, the major parameter to vary is the search-radius (r_{lim}). In my earlier simulations, I always stopped at about 1 grid-period, but now I have tried also larger values. With the present small number of scans, grid-step errors are common. This means in practice that

many doubles with larger separation than the serach-radius get spurious solutions at a smaller separation. The test-doubles have a rather smooth distribution in $\lg \rho$ up to 10 arcsec separation. The 'real' population of unknown doubles probably has fewer objects with large separations, but it is impossible to give quantitative predictions.

What I have done is to compare the solutions first for only the objects with STDDBL separation below r_{lim} , then for all the objects. For simplicity, a solution is considered 'good' (category a) if the separation agrees with STDDBL to within 0.1 arcsec and the magnitude-difference to within 0.2 magnitudes. A solution is considered 'spurious' (category b) if the separation is wrong but the magnitude-difference correct, and finally it is 'bad' (category c) if both quantities differ from the STDDBL solution. I also separate the results in three groups according to Δm_{eff} . Tables 1a and 1b gives the resulting percentages, which show rather definite trends with r_{lim} and Δm_{eff} . Most notably, the magnitude-differences come out correctly in a large majority of the solutions, and the fraction of 'bad' solutions does not increase with r_{lim} . (The individual figures for $\Delta m_{\text{eff}} > 2$ are rather uncertain because they are based on no more than 15-100 solutions. For $\Delta m_{\text{eff}} < 2$ there are 170-370 solutions).

Table 1a. Fraction (%) of 'good' (a), 'spurious' (b) or 'bad' (c) solutions for stars with true separations below r_{lim} .

$r_{\text{lim}}(\prime)$	$\Delta m_{\text{eff}} < 2$			$\Delta m_{\text{eff}} 2 - 3$			$\Delta m_{\text{eff}} > 3$		
	(a)	(b)	(c)	(a)	(b)	(c)	(a)	(b)	(c)
0.8	86	4	11	87	5	8	69	8	23
1.2	77	14	8	71	21	8	50	33	17
1.6	71	20	9	60	28	12	41	32	27
2.0	69	22	8	58	29	12	23	46	31
2.4	65	26	8	54	36	10	20	52	27
2.8	60	30	10	51	40	9	22	50	28

Table 1b. Fraction (%) of 'good' (a), 'spurious' (b) or 'bad' (c) solutions for stars with true separations up to $10''$.

$r_{\text{lim}}(\prime)$	$\Delta m_{\text{eff}} < 2$			$\Delta m_{\text{eff}} 2 - 3$			$\Delta m_{\text{eff}} > 3$		
	(a)	(b)	(c)	(a)	(b)	(c)	(a)	(b)	(c)
0.8	57	28	11	29	50	21	11	37	52
1.2	57	34	9	33	52	15	9	44	47
1.6	53	38	9	32	52	16	9	46	45
2.0	55	36	9	35	50	15	8	49	42
2.4	55	36	9	37	51	13	9	48	42
2.8	53	37	9	36	52	12	10	49	42

With the same parameters, and with search-radii up to 2.4 arcsec, I have then run SEEKDBL on the 2363 'suspected' CHF:s with at least 10 FOV-crossings. The result is a list with almost twice the number of 'new' doubles as obtained in June, but with a larger proportion of 'marginal' solutions with large Δm_{eff} . Table 2 summarizes the data, and in Fig. 4 the solutions for $r_{\text{lim}}=0.8$ (crosses) and 2.4 (circles) are plotted in a $\lg \rho / \Delta m$ -diagram. Using (illustratively) the percentages in Table 1b, the figures in Table 2 give estimated numbers of 'good', 'spurious' and 'bad' systems. Although the number of good solutions increases with r_{lim} , the

greatly increasing computing times set a practical limit for the search-radii. For the 1-year reductions, this will probably be at about 1.6 arcsec.

Table 2. Numbers of new doubles obtained by SEEKDBL for different search radii and different Δm_{eff} -intervals. The numbers of 'good' (a), 'spurious' (b) or 'bad' (c) solutions are estimated (roughly!) from the percentages in Table 1b.

$r_{\text{lim}}(^{\prime\prime})$	$\Delta m_{\text{eff}} < 2$			$\Delta m_{\text{eff}} 2 - 3$			$\Delta m_{\text{eff}} > 3$			all		
	(a)	(b)	(c)	(a)	(b)	(c)	(a)	(b)	(c)	(a)	(b)	(c)
0.8	77	36	14	56	97	41	22	74	105	155	208	160
1.2	81	48	13	67	106	31	21	105	112	169	259	156
1.6	84	60	14	72	117	36	23	115	113	179	292	163
2.0	86	56	14	77	110	33	21	128	110	184	294	157
2.4	86	56	14	84	116	30	24	128	112	195	301	156

Although the above numbers probably give the correct trends, they should not be taken too literally. Apart from the unknown distribution of the 'unknown doubles' in separation and magnitude difference, the data in Tables 1a and 1b compare only the SEEKDBL solutions with the STDDBL ones. An unknown fraction (typically 20-25% in simulations) of the STDDBL data also has grid-step errors, but probably the sum of the (a) and (b) categories is reasonably correct.

Fig. 4. The SEEKDBL 'new' solutions in a $\lg \rho / \Delta m_{\text{eff}}$ -diagram. Crosses are with search-radius $r_{\text{lim}} = 0.8$ arcsec (CPU-time 2.9 hours), circles with $r_{\text{lim}} = 2.4$ arcsec (CPU-time 13.5 hours). The dashed lines indicate $\Delta m_{\text{eff}} = 2.0, 3.2$ and 4.4.

6. The STDMUL program

The simulation version of the STDMUL program was run in 1988, and many modifications had to be made to be able to run it on the real data. One complication regards the start parameters. In the ICSPEC-file used to store Input Catalogue and improved data for singles and doubles, there is not enough room for all the components of a multiple. Therefore, a new 'MULSTAR'-file has been created, where the relative positions and magnitudes for the multiple star components are stored. With the IC 8 positions as input, a limited number of multiple star solutions has been obtained, but some work remains before the STDMUL program may be considered operational.

7. Conclusion

The CHF-generation process needs primarily a better photometric calibration (plus improved selection criteria for the suspected non-singles), but is otherwise in working order. The two main double-star solution programs (SEEKDBL and STDDBL) are ready for large-scale reductions, while finishing work on STDMUL is progressing. Programs for orbital and light-variable systems will not be available for the '1-year' processing.